

Infertility in Men of Reproductive Age and Causes

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Summary: The aim of this study is a statistical analysis of the causes of infertility in men of reproductive age living in the Bukhara region. The objects of examination were 85 infertile men of reproductive age who applied to the Bukhara Regional Medical Association within 6 months. Primary and secondary infertility were divided into groups. Of these, 60-65% (51 cases) are primary infertility and 30-35% (34 cases) are secondary infertility.

Keywords: infertility, reproductive, urinary tract infection.

Relevance. Infertility is one of the main reasons for the increase in the number of divorces in Uzbek families. Quarrels and various disagreements arise in families, which are considered the cell of society, due to childlessness. It should be noted that women's disease is the reason that only 40 percent of couples are unable to have children. Men are "guilty" in 45 percent of cases. The remaining 15 percent of cases are related to the incompatibility of the couple's organism, that is, immunological and other unique forms of infertility. The cell necessary for fertilization is developed by the male organism and, as everyone knows, it is the spermatozoon. There are three important problems underlying male infertility: poor sperm quality (impaired motility and viability); their number will decrease sharply; violation of their movement and excretion in the seminal tract.

Research purpose. The purpose of this study is to statistically analyze the causes of infertility in men of reproductive age.

Materials and methods. 85 infertile men of reproductive age who applied to the Bukhara district medical association within 6 months were taken as the object of inspections. Primary and secondary infertility groups were studied. The reasons were statistically analyzed.

Results: 51 primary infertile men, 30 (%) 34 secondary infertile men out of 85 referred patients (70%) were identified in the chart below.

Percentages of primary and secondary infertility in men of reproductive age

Age	Primary infertility	Secondary infertility
20-30 age	70 %	35 %
30-40 age	30 %	65 %

The most common causes of primary infertility in men aged 20-30 are: varicocele (in 15 percent of cases) - enlargement of the ovarian veins and scrotum (a special channel located in the scrotum and for the release of sperm). As a result of varicocele, the temperature rises in the ovaries, their activity is disturbed. This damages spermatozoa. Injuries and defects of male genital organs (failure to fall and twisting of eggs) - this reason occurs in 10-12 percent of men; infectious diseases (in 10 percent of cases).

Secondary infertility in men aged 30-40 is 65 percent, the main cause of which is sexually transmitted infections. These include gonorrhea, syphilis, chlamydia, trichomoniasis TORCH infections. Male genital organs, for example, prostate gland (prostatitis) or urinary tract (urethritis); Erectile Dysfunction: Erectile Dysfunction, Premature Ejaculation, etc. are examples.

Primary infertility in men aged 30-40 was found to be 35 percent. The reasons for this are endocrine diseases, immunological disorders: when the immune system stops, the body begins to produce special substances that can damage human spermatozoa. Hormonal disorders, for example, lack of male sex hormone - testosterone, obesity, alcoholism, smoking, drugs, certain medications, bad environment (radiation, pesticides, lack of vitamin C and zinc) and even disordered treatment of your body (clothing too tight, going to the sauna too often, going too far in sports activities). There are two main forms of male infertility - secretory and obturative. If the formation of spermatozoa in the tubules of the oviducts in the secretory form is disturbed, in the obturation form, obstacles appear in their path along the urinary tract. In the secretory form of infertility, the ovaries do not produce enough sperm for fertilization of the egg, or sperm motility is impaired, or most of the sperm have structural defects. The basis of male secretory infertility lies in influencing the ovaries to one degree or another. In the obturative form of infertility, the movement of spermatozoa through one or both sides of the seminiferous tract becomes difficult. In one-sided violation of transition, the number of spermatozoa is reduced, and in bilateral violation, their complete absence is observed.

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